

ID	Título	Ano
PS01	(Re) Learning fine motor hand movements with serious games	2022
PS02	2D Mobile Vocab Library Learning Application	2022
PS03	A 3D Board Game Using a Randomized Algorithm and AI to Improve English Vocabulary Retention and Fluency	2023
PS04	7-Day Math: A Mobile Visual Novel Game for Mathematics Education	2023
PS05	A Computer-Based Interactive Narrative and a Serious Game for Children With Asthma: Development and Content Validity Analysis	2021
PS06	A digital educational tool for learning the Aymara language in the region of Ayacucho, Peru	2021
PS07	A digital game for preserving food cultural heritage: design and evaluation of ThaiFoodAdventure game	2022
PS08	A Game-based Augmented Reality Navigation System to Support Makerspace User Education in a University Library	2023
PS09	A gamebased learning approach to improve students⇒ spelling in thai	2020
PS10	A Gamified Approach for Screening and Intervention of Dyslexia, Dysgraphia and Dyscalculia	2019
PS11	A gamified app on emotion recognition and anger management for pre-school children	2022
PS12	A Gamified Mobile Augmented Reality System for the Teaching of Astronomical Concepts	2019
PS13	A gamified mobile application for first-year student orientation to promote library services	2023
PS14	A holographic mobile-based application for practicing pronunciation of basic English vocabulary for Spanish speaking children	2019
PS15	A Mobile Application as Didactic Material to Improve Learning on Distributed Architectures	2020
PS16	A Mobile App to Increase Fruit and Vegetable Acceptance Among Finnish and Polish Preschoolers: Randomized Trial	2022
PS17	A mobile game as a support tool for children with severe difficulties in reading and spelling	2020
PS18	A Mobile Game for Automatic Emotion-Labeling of Images	2020
PS19	A New Interactive Gaming Approach for Enhancing Math Learning Among Marginalized Communities	2023
PS20	A Player-centered Design: Gamifying Self-learning to Cook on Mobile Application	2021
PS21	A Reusable Multiplayer Game for Promoting Active School Transport: Development Study	2022

PS22	A Serious Game for Mobile Phones used in a Software Engineering Course: Usability Evaluation and Educational Effectiveness	2021
PS23	A Serious Game to Self-Regulate Heart Rate Variability as a Technique to Manage Arousal Level Through Cardiorespiratory Biofeedback: Development and Pilot Evaluation Study	2023
PS24	A Serious Game to Train Rhythmic Abilities in Children With Dyslexia: Feasibility and Usability Study	2024
PS25	A Serious Game-Derived Index for Detecting Children With Heterogeneous Developmental Disabilities: Randomized Controlled Trial	2019
PS26	Adoption of Mobile Technology in Teaching Moral Values to Children: A Study in Malaysia	2020
PS27	An Android-Based Pre-Coding Method for Social Story Therapy Game Application for Children With Autism	2023
PS28	An app that changes mentalities about mobile learning—the eduPARK augmented reality activity	2019
PS29	An Educational Arabic Sign Language Mobile Application for Children with Hearing Impairment	2022
PS30	An Interactive Serious Mobile Game for Supporting the Learning of Programming in JavaScript in the Context of Eco-Friendly City Management	2020
PS31	Analysis of Usability Game Educational Learning of Wayang Characters Using Usability Scale System	2022
PS32	Android-Based Word Game Applications to Increase the Vocabulary of Deaf Children	2022
PS33	Android interactive word game in mother tongue for early childhood learners	2021
PS34	Application of alphazzzle writing for basic school children base on android	2019
PS35	Applying Gamification in Portuguese Learning	2021
PS36	AR-Child: Analysis, Evaluation, and Effect of Using Augmented Reality as a Learning Media for Preschool Children	2019
PS37	ARCode: Augmented Reality Application for Learning Elementary Computer Programming	2019
PS38	ARQuest: A Tangible Augmented Reality Approach to Developing Computational Thinking Skills	2019
PS39	Arunalu: Learning Ecosystem to Overcome Sinhala Reading Weakness due to Dyslexia	2020
PS40	Ask Dr. Discovery: the impact of a casual mobile game on visitorengagement with science museum content	2020
PS41	Assessing Ethoshunt as a Gamification-Based Mobile App in Ethics Education: Pilot Mixed-Methods Study	2020

PS42	AssociAR: Gamified Process for the Teaching of Children with Autism Through the Association of Images and Words	2020
PS43	Augmenting Early Childhood Education: The Integration of Augmented Reality in Promoting Personal Hygiene	2023
PS44	BeeLife: a mobile application to foster environmental awareness in classroom settings	2024
PS45	Body Mass Index Awareness using Game-based Learning in Malaysia: Game Design and Initial User Experiences	2019
PS46	Building Serious Game Design to Prepare University Students for The World of Work	2023
PS47	Can gamification help to teach Cybersecurity?	2022
PS48	ChaGame: A Serious Game for Educational Information About Chagas Disease in the Brazilian Amazon	2023
PS49	Chibumons: A Positive Effect on Game to Undergraduate Students	2020
PS50	ColourSpot, a novel gamified tablet-based test for accurate diagnosis of color vision deficiency in young children	2022
PS51	Contextualized mobile game-based learning application for computing education	2021
PS52	CS Challenger: Gamifying the Learning of Computer Science Concepts through a Mobile Application Platform	2019
PS53	Design and Implementation of Educational Game to Improve Arithmetic Abilities for Children	2019
PS54	Design of dayak kanayathn language learning mobile applications using gamification	2020
PS55	Design, development, and evaluation of divtcell app: Gamifying eukaryotic cell division and its effects on academic achievement	2023
PS56	Designing a Mobile Serious Game for Raising Awareness of DiabeticChildren	2020
PS57	Designing an extended smart classroom: An approach to game-based learning for IoT	2022
PS58	Designing and Implementing the MySusCof App-A Mobile App to Support Food Waste Reduction	2022
PS59	Designing educational game android to improve mathematical understanding ability on fraction	2019
PS60	Developing a Mobile Game Application to Enhance Learning Experience in Programmable Logic Controller (PLC) Wiring beyond the Laboratory	2024
PS61	Developing an android-based game for chemistry learners and its usability assessment	2020
PS62	Developing Gamified Mobile Learning to Increase Student Motivation to Learn WAN Technology for Vocational High School Students	2020

PS63	Developing gamification to improve mobile learning in web design course during the COVID-19 pandemic	2021
PS64	Developing mobile game application for introduction to financial accounting	2022
PS65	Development and application of a vocal health and hygiene game in adults	2019
PS66	Development and Effects of a Mobile Application for Safety Incident Prevention among Hospitalized Korean Children: A pilot Study of Feasibility and Acceptability	2020
PS67	Development and evaluation of a mobile game as an English learning tool for ESL learners	2021
PS68	Development and Evaluation of a Serious Game Application to Engage University Students in Critical Thinking About Health Claims: Mixed Methods Study	2023
PS69	Development and User Experiences of the Learn Viena Karelian Mobile Web Game	2019
PS70	Development and testing of a game-based digital intervention for working memory training in autism spectrum disorder	2021
PS71	Development and Validation of a Mobile Game for Culturally Sensitive Child Sexual Abuse Prevention Education in Tanzania: Mixed Methods Study	2021
PS72	Development of a Multiplication Game for Primary Students to Improve Learning Experience	2022
PS73	Development of a Mobile Game Application to Boost Students' Motivation in Learning English Vocabulary	2019
PS74	Development of a Serious Game to fight Childhood Obesity: "Barty"	2020
PS75	Development of Fun Hint Game Applications for Special Children on Smart Devices	2019
PS76	Development of Game-based Learning using A Mobile App for Students Fractions Learning	2021
PS77	Development Of Letter Learning Application For Early Childhood Using Mobile-Based Mda Framework	2023
PS78	Digital Games and Mobile Learning for Inclusion: Perspectives from Special Education Teachers	2023
PS79	Dilud: A Mobile Application to Reinforce Rote Learning in Elementary School Children with Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder	2023
PS80	DropQuest: Game-Based Learning for Chemistry	2022
PS81	Dynamic difficulty adjustment technique-based mobile vocabulary learning game for children with autism spectrum disorder	2022
PS82	Ecoaction mobile app: A game practice for eco-activist	2021
PS83	ECRIMO, an app to train first graders' spelling: Effectiveness and comparison between different designs	2023
PS84	Educational mobile augmented reality edupark game: Does it improve students learning?	2019

PS85	Educational mobile game for learning English words	2020
PS86	Effects of the use of the BAKE mobile application as an Educative instrument for teaching content for preschool education to Shipibo people in the community of Cantagallo, Lima, Peru	2020
PS87	Elemem: Interactive Digital Card Game for Chemistry	2020
PS88	eMATH: A Gamified Approach to Arithmetic Lessons	2023
PS89	Empowering Elementary Schools on Learning Math: A Development of Gamified Educational Mobile Application for Grade 3 Students	2019
PS90	Engaging African American Youth in the Development of a Serious Mobile Game for Sexual Health Education: Mixed Methods Study	2020
PS91	Equitable access to speech practice for rural Australian children using the SayBananas! mobile game	2023
PS92	Erudite Survivor: Usability Testing of a Gamification-based Mobile App for Disaster Awareness Among Children	2023
PS93	Evaluation User Acceptance of Mobile Virtual Reality Application for English Learning	2022
PS94	Exploring interest formation in english learning through xplorerafe+: A gamified ar mobile app	2021
PS95	Exploring Students' Use of a Mobile Application to Support Their Self-Regulated Learning Processes	2022
PS96	Exploring the Impact of Mobile Augmented Reality on COVID-19 Prevention Education in Primary Schools	2024
PS97	Exploring the Technological Acceptance of a Mobile Learning Tool Used in the Teaching of an Indigenous Language	2021
PS98	Fammeal: A Gamified Mobile Application for Parents and Children to Help Healthcare Centers Treat Childhood Obesity	2020
PS99	Field Playtesting with Experts' Constructive Interaction: An Evaluation Method for Mobile Games for Cultural Heritage	2021
PS100	First Aid Mobile Application for University Clinic using Predictive String Search Algorithm	2019
PS101	FightHPV: Design and Evaluation of a Mobile Game to Raise Awareness About Human Papillomavirus and Nudge People to Take Action Against Cervical Cancer	2019
PS102	Gam-mate: Gamification Applied to an Undergrad Discrete Math Course	2022
PS103	FUNologo: An Android-based Mobile Virtual Reality Assisted Learning with Speech Recognition Using Diamond-Square Algorithm for Children with Phonological Dyslexia	2023
PS104	Game education for child with disabled handle based on multimedia	2019
PS105	Gamification based mobile application as learning media innovation for basic programming lessons	2020

PS106	Gamification in the process of cognitive stimulation in children with Down syndrome	2023
PS107	Gamification of complex morphology learning: the case of Turkish	2023
PS108	Gamification of Mobile-based Japanese Language Shadowing	2019
PS109	Gamification to Improve Medication Adherence: A Mixed-method Usability Study for MedScrab	2023
PS110	Gamified Mobile Learning For Digital Business Model Course	2021
PS111	GAMIFYING "WHOLE-PERSON EDUCATION": THE DEVELOPMENT OF A MOBILE APPLICATION WITH AUGMENTED REALITY	2022
PS112	Gamifying Open Courseware on Mobile Application Using Player-Centered Design Approach	2023
PS113	Green Tycoon: A Mobile Application Game to Introduce Biorefining Principles in Green Chemistry	2020
PS114	Healthy Jeart. Developing an app to promote health among young people	2020
PS115	Hybridization Gamified: A Mobile App for Learning About Hybridization	2022
PS116	Ibigkas! 2.0: Directions for the Design of an Adaptive Mobile-Assisted Language Learning App	2019
PS117	Impact of Pediatric Mobile Game Play on Healthy Eating Behavior: Randomized Controlled Trial	2020
PS118	Impacts of augmented reality and a digital game on students' science learning with reflection prompts in multimedia learning	2020
PS119	Improving students' learning with a mobile augmented reality approach - the EduPARK game	2019
PS120	InCell VR: A Virtual Reality-based Application on Human Cell Division for Mobile Learning	2021
PS121	Individualized Edutainment and Parent Supportive Tool for ADHD Children	2020
PS122	Increasing motivation for cancer treatment adherence in children through a mobile educational game: a pilot study	2022
PS123	Instilling the Spirit of Ramadan to Malaysian Muslim Children through Mobile Game Approach	2022
PS124	Interactive educational animal identification game for primary schoolchildren with intellectual disability	2019
PS125	Introducing Sustainable Development Topics into Computer Science Education: Design and Evaluation of the Eco JSity Game	2021
PS126	Kabisa App: iOS-Based Application for Learning Sundanese Script with Game-Based Learning Implementation	2023
PS127	Kahaniyan - Designing for acquisition of Urdu as a second language	2019
PS128	Kiddy Manner: A Game-Based Mobile Application for Children Learning Thai Social Etiquette	2019

PS129	Learning by playing Init2Winit: How alignment knowledge increases educational aspirations and college plans in high school	2022
PS130	Lessons Learned from the Development of a Computerised Badge-based Reward Tool for Student Engagement in Learning Activities	2023
PS131	Manos que hablan: tool for teaching – learning the Mexican Sign Language for children with or without hearing disabilities	2020
PS132	MATS - An ADHD-Specific Mental Health App: Evidence-Based Recommendations for Designing Assistive Applications for ADHD Families	2023
PS133	Memory Training Interface for Elderly based on Mobile APP	2022
PS134	MILAGE LEARN plus : A Mobile Learning App to Aid the Students in the Study of Organic Chemistry	2021
PS135	Mobile application for the dissemination, learning and revitalisation of the native Muniche language in the Peruvian Amazon, in the context of Covid-19	2021
PS136	Mobile Augmented Reality Application with Multi-Interaction for Learning Solutions on the Topic of Computer Network Devices (Effectiveness, Interface, and Experience Design)	2020
PS137	Mobile Educational Game 'Imuno' to Teach Human Immune System	2023
PS138	MOBILE GAME: EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGY FOR HOME CARE OF PATIENTS UNDERGOING LIVER TRANSPLANTATION; [MOBILE GAME: TECNOLOGIA EDUCACIONAL PARA CUIDADOS DOMICILIARES DO PACIENTE SUBMETIDO AO TRANSPLANTE HEPÁTICO]; [JUEGO MÓVIL: TECNOLOGÍA EDUCATIVA PARA LA ATENCIÓN DOMICILIARIA DE PACIENTES SOMETIDOS A TRASPLANTE DE HÍGADO]	2024
PS139	Mobile Malaysian Sign Language Application	2022
PS140	Mobile Serious Game using Augmented Reality for Increasing Quality of Learning	2021
PS141	Motivational benefits and usability of a handheld Augmented Reality game for anatomy learning	2022
PS142	Moving beyond Limitations: Designing the Helpdys App for Children with Dyslexia in Rural Areas	2021
PS143	Multimedia augmented reality game for learning math	2022
PS144	OOP Codes: Teaching Object-Oriented Programming Concepts Through a Mobile Serious Game	2021
PS145	Optimizing Child Nutrition Education With the Foodbot Factory Mobile Health App: Formative Evaluation and Analysis	2020
PS146	Organic Fanatic: A Quiz-Based Mobile Application Game to Support Learning the Structure and Reactivity of Organic Compounds	2020
PS147	Perceived effectiveness of an innovative mobile-based serious game on the improvement of soft skills in minimally invasive surgical training	2023
PS148	Persuasive Application for Sex Education	2023

PS149	Pic2Program - An educational android application teaching computational thinking	2020
PS150	Preservations and rescue of the Omagua language through the use of a mobile application in homes in the San Joaquin de Omaguas community in Loreto, Peru	2021
PS151	QuizHuntAR: A location-based Augmented Reality game for education	2021
PS152	Ramadan Spirit: A Digital Game Incorporating Malaysian Culture to Teach Malaysian Muslim Children the Islamic Essence of Ramadan	2023
PS153	Reha@Stroke - A Mobile Application to Support People Suffering from a Stroke Through Their Rehabilitation	2019
PS154	Roadmap for the Development of EnLang4All: A Video Game for Learning English	2023
PS155	Scool - Game-based learning in computer science class A case study in secondary education	2019
PS156	Serious Game Application Development for Learning Battle of Surabaya	2022
PS157	Soceng Warriors: Game-Based Learning to Increase Security Awareness Against Social Engineering Attacks	2022
PS158	STD PONG 2.0: Field Evaluation of a Mobile Persuasive game for Discouraging Risky Sexual Behaviours among Africans Youths	2021
PS159	Students' evaluation of the 'web technologies' android application for higher education	2019
PS160	The Development and Application of Augmented Reality Educational Game in English Learning	2022
PS161	The Effectiveness of the Foodbot Factory Mobile Serious Game onIncreasing Nutrition Knowledge in Children	2020
PS162	The effects of STEAM-based mobile learning on learning achievement and cognitive load	2023
PS163	The Influence of Gamification on Quran Reading Learning	2023
PS164	There's an app for that: Teaching residents to communicate diagnostic uncertainty through a mobile gaming application	2022
PS165	Trafik Moris: A Serious Game for Learning Traffic Behavior and Safety	2022
PS166	Tsiimene: Mobile application to improve the knowledge and revitalisation of the Bora language in the context of COVID-19 in Loreto Peru	2022
PS167	Tsunami Fighters: Collaborative Multilingual Mobile Game for Earthquake and Tsunami Disaster Preparedness Education	2020
PS168	Unique English: An English Learning Application for Remedial Program Using Gamification Approach	2020
PS169	Usability, Acceptability, Feasibility, and Effectiveness of a Gamified Mobile Health Intervention (Triumpf) for Pediatric Patients: Qualitative Study	2019

PS170	User Evaluation on a Mobile Augmented Reality Game-based Application as a Learning Tool for Biology	2023
PS171	Using Challenges to Enhance a Learning Game for Pronunciation Training of English as a Second Language	2020
PS172	Using Distance Communication for the User-Centered Development of a Smartphone-Based Serious Game for Children With Type 1 Diabetes: Participatory Design Approach	2022
PS173	Virtual Laboratory-Based Game Application: The Quality and Its Effects Towards Students' Motivation and Self-Regulated Learning	2022
PS174	WAWA: Mobile educational tool for learning the Kichwa language for the communities of the Napo River in Loreto, Peru	2022
PS175	Winning could mean success, yet losing doesn't mean failure"—Using a mobile serious game to facilitate science learning in middle school	2023
PS176	WISE game: wireless interactive software educational game	2021